

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B294
Date: 18 June 2007
Take Off: 14:10:05
Landing: 18:56:48
Flight Time: 4h 46m 43s

Campaign: GERBIL

Operating Area: Agadir - Nouakchott

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	CCM2 / Core Chem.	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Mission scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
7	Mission scientist 2	Ben Johnson	Met Office
8	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	ENG	Martin Darling	Avalon
10	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
11	FAAM Ops	Steve Ball	FAAM
12	Neph / PSAP / SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office

Flight Track:

B294 Track 18-JUN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B294
 Date: 18 Jun 2007
 Project: Gerbil
 Location: Agadir - Nouakchott

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
135146		CGPS	0.23 kft	131	b294cgps.log
135158		GIN	0.24 kft	131	booted
135210		DRS	0.24 kft	131	checked
135226		INU	0.24 kft	131	to nav
135944		Start-Up	0.24 kft	131	
141005		T/O	0.22 kft	271	Agadir
141205		psap	3.1 kft	232	flow on
141239		twc	4.2 kft	253	one heater
141314		heimann	5.0 kft	253	open
141440		video	5.0 kft	246	#1 FFC; #2 UFC
141519		twc	5.0 kft	246	two heaters; statusok
141816		heimann	5.0 kft	246	cal 10
141911	143550	Profile 1	5.1 - 23.0 kft	247	
142101		manouver	7.0 kft	225	airspace
142146		JW	8.2 kft	155	zero
142340		!RUN 1.1	11.1 kft	158	5000ft run before 14:19
142503		profile 1	13.2 kft	223	stable path resumed
142947		video	17.5 kft	251	#2 now DFC
143333		WxRx	21.1 kft	250	recording
143551	145928	Run 2.1	23.0 kft	250	
143823		heimann	23.0 kft	251	cal 09 - run 2.1 at transit speed
145231		bbr	23.0 kft	251	retract
145929	150310	Profile 2	23.0 - 25.0 kft	248	p2 start 15:00:20
150020		profile 2	23.0 kft	222	
150311	164504	Run 3.1	25.0 kft	224	p2 start 15:00:20
153511		Sonde 1	25.0 kft	221	
154853		Video	25.0 kft	208	#3 FFC, #4DFC starte
160021		heimann	25.0 kft	214	cal 09
161513		Sonde 2	25.0 kft	209	
163604		sonde 1	25.0 kft	204	splash 154459
163626		sonde 2	25.0 kft	204	splash 162456
164415		Sonde 3	25.0 kft	170	
164505	171520	Profile 3	25.0 - 0.10 kft	163	
165803		P3	12.5 kft	163	interrupted
165954		P3	12.6 kft	343	resumed
170018		bbr	12.2 kft	344	extended
171237		qnh	1.7 kft	339	1016
171417		qnh	0.59 kft	337	1015
171546		Video	0.35 kft	315	#5 FFC, #6 DFC
171717	171743	Orbit 1	0.61 - 0.50 kft	082	050M start
171817	171926	Orbit 2	0.53 - 0.54 kft	207	210M start
172214	172321	Orbit 3	0.57 - 0.55 kft	118	110M start
172456	172604	Orbit 4	0.56 - 0.53 kft	036	030M start
172740	173339	Run 4.1	0.09 kft	326	100ft
172822		heimann	0.09 kft	324	cal 10
173520	175904	Profile 4	0.09 - 20.0 kft	155	
173550		bbr	0.32 kft	152	extend
173720		roc	1.4 kft	153	to 1000ft/min
174656		P4	10.0 kft	106	interrupt @ f1100
174809		P4	10.0 kft	343	resumed
180110	183531	Run 5.1	20.0 - 19.9 kft	168	
181008		bbr	20.0 kft	167	extend
181500		bbr	20.0 kft	166	retract
182256		Sonde 4	20.0 kft	166	
185648		Land	0.12 kft	034	Nouakchott

B294 Track 18-JUN-07

FAAM Sortie Brief

GERBIL TRANSIT FROM MOROCCO TO NOUAKCHOTT – PLAN A (IF DUST PRESENT OVER OCEAN)

Flight No: B294

Date: 18th June 2007

Trial objectives:

1. Measure the effects of Saharan dust aerosol on outgoing shortwave and longwave radiation over the Atlantic ocean.
2. Measure insitu properties of Saharan dust aerosol over the Atlantic ocean.

Location: Running southwards from Morocco to Nouakchott, approximately 100 miles out from the Coastline.

Point A = AMDIB (~21N, 100 miles off coast)

Point B = 25mins south from point A.

Desired weather:

High loadings of mineral dust aerosol flowing out from the Sahara. Cloud-free essential for evaluating radiative effects of dust.

Special requirements:

Drosondes desired to characterise temperature and humidity profile. This allows more accurate determination of aerosol radiative effects.

Instruments of particular importance:

Nephelometers (run both as dry)

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

SWS

SHIMS

AIRES

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Agadir (Morocco) around 14Z and head SW over ocean.
2. Hold at 5000ft for a few minutes until all scientists are ready [10mins].
3. Profile (1000ft/min) back down to 500ft above ocean surface, or to 1000ft above any low-level marine stratus [5 min, T=15mins].
4. SLR for 10mins at this level (to characterise downwelling radiation, cancel manouvers 2 and 3 if significant cirrus above) [10mins, T=25mins].
5. Profile ascent at 1000ft/min to FL240 heading Southwest [25mins, T=50mins]. Continue running SW parallel and at least 30miles off coast.
6. Run at FL240 heading south-southwest at least 30miles off the coast towards point A). Science speed not necessary [120mins, T=165mins].
7. Drop sondes out during this run, once every 15 minutes (up to 8 sondes required), once south of Canary Islands.
8. At point A, slow to science speed and perform profile descent at 1000ft/min, down to 100ft [25mins, T =190mins]. End of profile defines point B.

9. Recover to 600ft and perform series of 4 orbits at maximum bank angle (60 degrees?) at 600ft [10mins, T=200mins].
10. Series of 3 stacked SLRs running parallel to coast between point A and B, through the dust layer (predicted to be between FL070 and FL170), e.g. FL090, FL120, FL150. 15mins for each run with profiles between runs at 1000ft/min [70mins, T=270].
11. Profile descent at 1000ft/min down to low-levels [10mins, T=280mins].
12. Land at Nouakchott [5 mins, T=285mins = 4:45].

Mission scientist debrief

B294 – GERBILS transit from Agadir to Nouakchott

Location

Over ocean running parallel to coast.

Mission aims

Radiative effect of Saharan dust flowing out over Atlantic from high altitude and low-level. In situ measurements of dust.

Weather

Mostly clear skies except for broken stratocumulus / fair weather cumulus below in some places. Very little aerosol until about 21.5N, then reasonably thick dust from

Flight plans

Take off from Agadir (Morocco) at 14:10. Profile up to 5000ft and run over ocean for 5mins at 5000ft. The later part of that run (14:14-14:19) should be OK for a clear sky radiation calculation as no cloud above or below and 10-20miles (sufficient distance off coast by end of run). Profile ascent to FL230, followed by a long run, approximately parallel to coast and 30-50miles off coast. Profile up to FL250, then continue the run as before. Two sondes dropped out enroute to AMDIB (20.5N, 18W) and one at AMDIB. At AMDIB a broken profile descent was made to 100ft, followed by orbits roughly beneath AMDIB. A 5 min SLR beneath AMDIB at 100ft, then a broken profile back up to FL200 finishing at AMDIB. The high level flying was resumed from AMDIIB for 30mins, though at FL200 rather than FL250 as before. A fast descent and landing at Nouakchott at 19:00

There was no cirrus above for most of the flight, just a little around 20N at 18:00. SWS and AIRES were pointing down for high level work and up for low-level work. During profiles SWS was pointing zenith on descending and nadir on ascending profiles. Earlier parts of the run down the coast had broken stratocumulus/cumulus below, later parts of this run (after 15:40, i.e. south of 26N) were completely free of cloud below. The radiative effect of dust was negligible ($5Wm^{-2}$ according to Jim H) during northern part of high-level runs but increased to $30-35Wm^{-2}$ by AMDIB.

Summary

This flight almost follows a classic GERBIL radiation pattern (as in scientific planning diagram) over a dust layer over the ocean. Also good clear sky measurements further north. No in situ SLRs through dust but pcpas flow was no running anyway. No other instrument problems to report.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.294**
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Date 18/6/07

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1410	T10	/	W	AGADIR	MOROCCO
			W		Scattered stcu tops ~5,500 FT (1/8)
					fairly well mixed BL, slight decoupling.
					Neph ~30x10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻¹ cloud mainly over land less out over ocean
1413	Run11	FLO50	250		Now over ocean no cloud ahead
1419 11	P1	FLO50	250		Danger area ahead scupper's Danger area ahead scupper's chance of low-level work
					climb slightly broken by sharp turns due to air traffic diverting us
14351	End	FL230			Running into area of
14351	R2.1	FL230	250	29.5, 10.7 N W	scattered low-level stcu 2/8
145928	End				This will be problem for radiation work
145929	P2	FL230			1414-1419 at FLO50 (Run 11) should be OK for clear sky radiation assessment, BBRs suggest minimal interference of land
	End	FL250			
150311	R3.1	FL250	SW		
1520	"	"	SW		Clear patch below with no cloud below us
1520	"	"	"		NO cirrus anywhere yet on this flight.
1520					SWS & AIRES both NADIR
1520					SWS doing Zenith occasionally too
1540	"	"	"		Deviating a little closer to east to avoid cloud below.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....**294**
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Date **18/6/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
153511		FL250	S		Sonde 1
1550					Becoming totally clear of cloud below. Good for SWS & AIRES. Both are NADIR.
1550					We are about 30 miles off coast
161530		"	"	23.3N 16.7W	Sonde 2
1625		"	"	22.5N	Starting to go under dust layer. BBR lower has rising signal
164505	P3	FL250			Dust top at FL180
1653	"	FL180			
164415		FL250	"		Sonde 3
165803	Interrupt	FL125			Interrupt profile to turn onto reciprocal heading
165954	Resume		N		Solar zenith angle = 52°
					Sea state completely calm
					Main Aerosol base ~ 5,000ft
					little layer ~ 300ft
					Neph

1:15
51
33
70
610

16

20
15
10

Height

150 x 10⁻⁶ m⁻¹

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.294**
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Date 18/6/07

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1715 -1725	End p3		N	AMDIB	Series of 4 orbits beneath AMDIB (21N,
172740	R4.1				Run at 100ft with SWS & ARES zenith Finishing at AMDIB.
1735	R4 Intermitt	100ft FL100	S S-N	AMDIB	(20.5N, 18W)
1	End	FL200	N		
	RS-1	FL200	S	AMDIB	AMDIB
				FL250	
					drop sands
					dust
					FL100
					FL125
					FL200
					4 orbits
					AGADIR
					NOUAK CHOTT
1758	"	FL180		21N, 18W	dust top at FL180 Corresponds to weak inversion

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B294

Date : 18/06/07

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	Leak to cabin air. Data incorrect.
O₃	None
NO_x	None
TDLAS	None

B294_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

13:35:03.96 --- - - - -
13:35:03.96 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
13:35:03.96 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period / tVIS/ tNIR /
                               Comment +++
13:35:03.96 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B294
13:35:03.96 --- - - - -
13:35:33.71 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
13:35:51.51 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR OK
13:36:16.24 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:36:21.26 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR FAILED
13:36:27.96 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:36:34.41 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
13:36:35.76 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
13:36:37.11 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
13:36:50.13 LSH - - - - Instrument closed.
13:36:53.33 SWS - - - - Instrument closed.
13:37:24.55 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:37:45.06 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
13:37:57.68 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS FAILED NIR FAILED
13:39:37.08 --- - - - -
13:39:37.08 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
13:39:37.08 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period / tVIS/ tNIR /
                               Comment +++
13:39:37.08 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B294
13:39:37.08 --- - - - -
13:39:50.23 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:39:53.20 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:39:59.79 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:40:15.52 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:40:18.99 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:40:22.19 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:40:28.37 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:40:28.38 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:40:28.38 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:40:53.11 SWS - - - - Idling
13:40:55.26 USH - - - - Idling
13:40:57.33 LSH - - - - Idling
13:41:15.61 SWS - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
13:41:20.34 SWS - - 750 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
13:41:26.02 USH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
13:41:32.11 USH - - 500 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
13:41:35.82 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
13:41:39.07 LSH - - 500 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
13:41:42.04 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:41:42.05 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:41:42.05 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:41:48.19 USH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 250ms.
13:41:52.69 USH - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 75ms.
13:41:57.92 SWS - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 75ms.
13:43:44.97 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:43:45.46 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:43:45.48 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:43:50.44 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:43:53.40 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:43:53.59 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:43:59.02 SWS - - - - Idling
13:44:00.63 USH - - - - Idling
13:44:02.30 LSH - - - - Idling
13:55:41.47 --- - - - - *** Where are the Gerbils?
13:55:55.64 SWS - - 400 - NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
13:56:00.19 USH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
13:56:04.11 USH - - 400 - NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
13:56:09.64 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
14:10:18.98 --- - - - - *** take off from Agadir
14:10:24.86 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:10:24.87 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:10:24.88 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:10:53.33 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
14:11:08.56 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:11:08.58 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:11:08.59 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:11:13.20 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:11:13.40 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:11:14.97 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:11:15.17 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.

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14:11:16.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:19.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:19.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:21.20	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:11:24.40	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:11:31.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:11:34.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:11:36.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:37.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:11:38.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:45.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:41.27	LSH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:15:55.17	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 500ms.
14:15:59.23	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
14:16:02.37	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
14:19:25.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** start P1
14:23:02.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** to 168R for SWS
14:30:43.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 10F
14:30:56.73	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
14:33:47.15	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
14:33:55.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:55.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:56.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:59.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:03.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:03.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:51.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** end pl start R1
14:35:59.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** at FL230
14:36:29.00	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:36:33.75	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
14:36:40.42	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
14:36:51.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:54.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:59.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:59.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:54.87	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:39:21.16	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:40:00.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** scattered Cu below. Data likely to be polluted
14:40:14.41	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:42:13.56	---	-	-	-	-	***
14:42:13.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:14.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:42:39.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:39.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:39.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:44.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:42:47.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:42:47.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:17.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:47:22.46	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
14:47:27.46	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
14:47:31.07	LSH	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 75ms.
14:47:37.24	LSH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 750ms.
14:47:43.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:49:04.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:12.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:49:16.27	LSH	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 1000ms.
14:49:23.16	USH	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 1000ms.
14:49:25.96	SWS	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 1000ms.
14:49:34.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:49:42.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:59:30.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** end r1
15:00:20.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** start P2
15:01:18.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** tp FL250
15:03:17.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** end p2 start r2
15:03:35.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** R3.1
15:05:22.12	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
15:05:24.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:32.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:19:12.36	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:19:50.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 5F
15:22:46.79	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:57:31.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:31.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:31.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:35.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:39.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

15:57:39.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:35:58.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:35:59.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:35:59.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:36:03.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:07.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:07.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:20.44	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
16:36:24.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:36:32.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:38:57.92	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 150ms.
16:39:01.80	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
16:39:05.13	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
16:39:07.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:12.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:50:40.23	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:50:54.59	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
16:50:59.91	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
16:51:03.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:51:11.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:54:08.21	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
16:54:10.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:54:18.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:57:57.86	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
16:58:01.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:58:09.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:58:32.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** in a turn
17:03:42.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** good dust for the past hour
17:04:45.78	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
17:04:48.61	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
17:04:51.46	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:04:55.32	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
17:04:59.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:04:59.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:04:59.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:05:07.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:05:07.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:05:07.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:07:56.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** out of dust layer at FL060
17:15:20.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile descent at 100ft.
17:15:43.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** to 600ft for orbits
17:16:04.91	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 75ms.
17:16:11.97	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
17:16:17.41	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 30ms.
17:16:22.89	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
17:16:27.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:16:29.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:18:00.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** start orbit 1
17:18:19.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** start orbit 1
17:19:24.73	SWS	-	500	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 500ms.
17:19:28.00	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 10ms.
17:19:31.56	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 50ms.
17:19:35.78	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 50ms.
17:19:38.64	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 200ms.
17:19:41.66	USH	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 10ms.
17:19:45.62	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
17:19:47.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:19:47.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:19:47.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:19:48.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:19:48.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:19:52.63	USH	-	500	-	-	Sample period changed from 1000ms to 500ms.
17:19:55.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:15.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** start orbit 2
17:22:24.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** 110 heading start
17:23:29.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** end orbit
17:24:34.40	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 250ms.
17:24:37.05	LSH	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 250ms.
17:24:38.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:24:41.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:24:57.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** start orbit 3
17:25:03.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** 030 start heading
17:25:19.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** 600ft 55deg aob left hand turn
17:26:13.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** end orbit
17:27:22.01	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 250ms.
17:27:27.99	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 750ms.
17:27:40.19	USH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 300ms.

17:27:44.40	USH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
17:27:48.48	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
17:27:51.26	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 750ms.
17:27:56.71	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 500ms.
17:28:01.46	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:28:05.92	LSH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 750ms.
17:28:16.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:16.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:16.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:24.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:24.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:24.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:41.50	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:33:54.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run at 100ft
17:35:13.23	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:35:19.22	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 500ms.
17:35:39.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** start P4 ascent from 100ft
17:35:48.49	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:35:51.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:35:59.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:36:20.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws telescope to 176deg
17:38:14.29	SWS	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 1000ms.
17:38:17.88	USH	-	1000	-	-	Sample period changed from 500ms to 1000ms.
17:41:13.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 172deg in profile ascent
17:46:47.00	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:47:08.11	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
17:47:12.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:47:20.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:47:32.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** in a turn
17:51:33.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** not any more
17:51:56.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 172
17:55:30.80	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
17:55:33.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:55:43.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:01:22.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** start r5.1 at\FL200
18:06:26.10	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:10:30.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** lower bbr shutter closed
18:10:48.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** shutter open again
18:11:23.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** still closed
18:14:58.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** shutter open again
18:24:56.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:24:57.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:24:57.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:25:04.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:25:05.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:25:05.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:35:22.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run
18:35:23.93	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:36:57.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 0deg (NADIR)
18:40:46.65	USH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
18:40:50.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:40:58.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B294 page 1 of 5
 Date: 18/06/07 Operator(s): S. Rogers Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2
 Loc./Notes: Transfer - AGADIR TO NOUAKCHOTT + SOME SCARY ORBITS.

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments	Cut 1x1 View 1x1
12 35:35	a.k.f.m	1x60	C	C	71	31	*DRS times are 1 hour out	
12 36 19	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	due to operator confusion when	
12 39 00	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	setting the ARIES clock. Doh!	
12 39 36	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	(so 1st entry 12:35:35 should be <u>13:35:35</u>)	
12 40 17	"	120x1	Z	○	71	31	On the ground. A little hazy above	
12 41 43	"	1x60	C	C	71	31		
12 42 22	"	1x60	H	C	71	31		
~13 10	TAKEOFF							
13 35 50	R2-1 FL230	1x60	C	C	71	31		
13 36 50		"	H	C	71	31		
13 37		120x1	Z	○	70	31	Clear above (v. thin haze?)	↑
13 38 48		"	N	C	71	31		
13 39 58		1x60	C	C	71	31		
13 40 35		"	H	C	71	31		
13 41 23		360x1	N	C	71	31	Broken Cu below	↓
13 44 43		1x60	C	C	71	31		
13 45 20		"	H	C	71	31		
13 46 45		360x1	N	C	71	30		↓
13 49 19		1x60	C	C	71	31		
13 49 57		"	H	C	71	31		
13 50 35		360x1						
13 56		1x60	C	C	71	31		
13 56 50		"	H	C	71	30		
	R2↑							
14 03 21	FL250?	1x60	C	C				
14 04 00		"	H	C	71	31		
14 04 53		360x1	N	C	71	31	Small Cu below.	
14 08 03		1x60	C	C	71	30		
14 08 38		"	H	C	71	31		
14 09 31		480x1	N	C	71	31		
14 13 39		1x60	C	C	71	30		

ARIES flight log

Flight: *B294*

page *2* of *5*

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
14 14 22	FL250	1x60	H	C	71	31	
14 15 04	"	360x1	N	C	71	30	Mostly clear, some small Cu. ↓
14 18 18		1x60	C	C	71	31	
14 18 5-		"	H	C	71	31	
14 19 32		120x1	Z	☉	70	30	Clear above ↑
14 20 42		120x1	N	C	71	31	
14 21 50		1x60	C	C	71	31	
14 22 26		"	H	C	71	31	
14 23 11		480x1	N	C	71	31	Clear below ↕
14 27 18		1x60	C	C	71	30	
14 27 55		"	H	C	71	31	
14 28 58		360x1	N	C	71	31	Cloud below, clear later ↓
14 32 09		1x60	C	C	71	30	
14 32 43		"	H	C	71	31	
14 33 28		360x1	N	C	71	31	14:35 Sonda ↓
14 36 37		1x60	C	C	71	30	
14 37 13		"	H	C	71	31	
14 37 55		360x1	N	C	71	30	Mostly clear, some small Cu. ↓
14 41 03		1x60	C	C	71	31	
14 41 40		"	H	C	71	31	
14 42 22		480x1	N	C	71	30	↓
14 46 32		1x60	C	C	71	31	
14 47 15		"	H	R	71	31	
14 48 07		360x1	N	C	71	30	Clear below ↓
14 51 17		1x60	C	C	71	30	
14 51 53		"	H	C	71	31	
14 52 36		360x1	N	C	71	31	Clear below ↓
14 55 46		1x60	C	C	71	31	
14 56 23		"	H	C	71	31	
14 57 07		360x1	N	C	71	31	Clear below ↓
15 00 13		1x60	C	C	70	31	

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13294

page 3 of 5

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
15 00 57	FL250	1x60	H	C	71	30	
15 01 39		360x1	N	C	71	31	Clear below ↓
15 04 47		1x60	C	C	71	31	
15 05 23		"	H	C	71	30	
15 06 05		360x1	N	C	71	31	Clear below ↓
15 09 12		1x60	C	C	71	30	
15 09 48		"	H	C	71	31	
15 10 33		360x1	N	C	71	31	Clear below ↓
15 13 40		1x60	C	C	71	31	
15 14 16		"	H	C	71	31	
15 14 55		360x1	N	C	70	31	Clear below Same 1515 ↓
15 18 01		1x60	C	C	71	30	
15 18 37		"	H	C	70	31	
15 19 17		360x1	N	C	71	31	Clear below ↓
15 22 25		1x60	C	C	71	31	
15 22 59		"	H	C	71	30	
15 23 43		360x1	N	C	71	31	Clear below ↓
15 26 47		1x60	C	C	70	31	
15 27 23		"	H	C	71	31	
15 28 03		360x1	N	C	71	31	Clear below - dust? ↓
15 31 11		1x60	C	C	71	31	
15 31 46		"	H	C	71	30	
15 32 30		360x1	N	C	71	31	Clear of cloud - dust! ↓
15 35 39		1x60	C	C	71	31	
15 36 25		"	H	C	71	30	
15 37 05		360x1	N	C	71	31	Dust? ↓
15 40 11		1x60	C	C	71	30	
15 40 45		"	H	C	71	31	
15 41		240x1	N	C	71	31	↓
15 43 36		1x60	C	C	71	30	
15 44 11		"	H	C	71	31	1544. Same

ARIES flight log

Flight: B294

page 4 of 5

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs][co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
15 58 04	FL125	1x60	C	C	71	31	
15 58 41	"	"	H	C	71	31	
16 16 30		"	C	C			
16 17 00		120 71	H	C			
16 17 18	600ft?	120x1	Z	O			Orbit 1 Scary. ↑
16 19 22		"	Z	O			orbit end. ↑
			CH	O			Script 1 cold+hot Absolute
16 22		120x1	Z	O			Orbit ↑
16 23 21		1x60	CH	O			Script 1 cold+hot.
16 24 56		120x1	Z	O			Orbit. ↑
16 26			CH	C	70	34	Script 1 cold+hot
	600ft??	1x60	C	C			↑ check
16 27		"	H	C	71	34	
16 28		240x1	Z	O	70	34	↑
16 30 35		120x1	N	C	71	35	↓
16 31 45		1x60	C	C	71	34	
16 32 30		"	H	C	71	34	
17 01 10	FL200?	1x60	C	C	71	31	
17 01		"	H	C	71	30	
17 02 29		360x1	N	C	71	31	Dusty below ↓
17 05 38		1x60	C	C	71	31	
17 06 26		"	H	C	71	31	
17 07 07		360x1	N	C	71	30	v. dusty ↓
17 10 16		1x60	C	C	71	30	
17 10 56		"	H	C	71	31	
17 11 53		360x1	N	C	71	31	↓
17 16 03		1x60	C	C	71	31	
17 15 40		"	H	C	71	31	
17 16 24		480x1	N	C	71	30	↓
17 20 31		1x60	C	C	71	31	
17 21 06		"	H	C	71	30	

Flight:

B294

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevezorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:41:26

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

ADA:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

26/06/2007 11:48:39

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B294

Date: 18 June 2007

Instruments

1. dry neph relative humidity suspect
2. nevz U/S

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

3

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Terra:
17th June

Aqua:
17th June

NAME version 816

Title: Global forecast

Valid at 1200UTC 18/06/2007

From 2000 – 5000 ft agl Air concentration

From 5000 – 10000 ft agl Air concentration

Sunday 17 June 2007 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Monday 18 June 2007 12UTC

Low, L+M, Medium, M+H, High, H+L, H+M+L clouds

Dust conc 20.000o merid xsect

At 12Z on 18/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 17/ 6/2007

Dust conc 17.500o merid xsect

At 12Z on 18/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 17/ 6/2007

Dust conc 12.500o merid xsect

At 12Z on 18/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 17/ 6/2007

06Z_170607 AOD T+36

At 12Z on 18/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 17/ 6/2007

EAA011 MSG volcanic ash/dust 17 Jun 2007 1330 UTC

Brightness temperature difference (K)

EAA051 MSG dust product 17 Jun 2007 1300 UTC

B294 Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

10z_180607 Surface Dust concentration T+36

At 12Z on 19/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 18/ 6/2007

$1e-5$ $1e-4$ 0.001 0.01 0.1 1

2000-5000ft Dust concentration T+36

$1e-5$ $1e-4$ 0.001 0.01 0.1 1

10z_180607 AOD T+36

At 12Z on 19/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 18/ 6/2007

0.05 0.1 0.2 0.4 0.8 1.6 3.2 6.4 12.8

Dust conc 12.500o merid xsect

At 12Z on 19/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 18/ 6/2007

Dust conc 15.000o merid xsect

At 12Z on 19/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 18/ 6/2007

Dust conc 17.500o merid xsect

At 12Z on 19/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 18/ 6/2007

Dust conc 20.000o merid xsect

At 12Z on 19/ 6/2007, from 00Z on 18/ 6/2007

Flight B294 17:57:39

Heading 342 deg Speed 283 knots Height 18.8kft Press 488mb

Lat 20°54.0'N Long 17°42.0'W Wind 3 ms-1/ 210 deg

Temp -8.6C Dewpoint -29.87C

From 16:41:20 to now

Current values			
+++++ PRESSURE HEIGHT	18.83	Kft	⊙ All
+++++ NEPH BLUE SP	-0.72	m-1	⌒
+++++ NEPH GREEN SP	0.68	m-1	⌒
+++++ NEPH RED SP	0.74	m-1	⌒

$\tau = 0.5$

$\rightarrow AOD = 0.5 \text{ at } 0.55 \mu\text{m}$

Normalised DRE = $80 \text{ Wm}^{-2} / \tau$

$DRE = 90 - 50 = 40 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$

$\rightarrow NDRE = 80 \text{ Wm}^{-2} / \tau$

New plot, same times

Reflection of SW radiation

Flight B294 16:43:03

Heading 175 deg Speed 310 knots Height 25.0kft Press 375mb

Lat 21°0.0'N Long 17°48.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 175 deg

Temp -21.91C Dewpoint -49.04C

From 13:42:12 to now

Current values			
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	60183	secs	⊙ All
UPPER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	677.62	W m-2	⌋
UPPER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	372.38	W m-2	⌋
LOWER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	84.74	W m-2	⌋
LOWER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	19.33	W m-2	⌋

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B294:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Nephelometer	No operator on GERBIL

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	05 Sep 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
1 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras
2 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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